

UHP-SWSSC FILLED GFRP TUBES UNDER COMBINED SUSTAINED LOAD AND SEAWATER EXPOSURE

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ABSTRACT

This experimental investigation evaluates the durability of GFRP tubular composites filled with marine resource-based ultra-high-performance concrete under combined sustained loading and seawater exposure at an elevated temperature. Material properties of the FRPs with different diameter to thickness ratio were determined in both longitudinal and hoop directions. Creep strains were monitored in both directions for 2000 hours, and a comprehensive analysis was conducted on the axial compressive stress-strain response, stiffness, and failure modes of unconditioned and conditioned composite specimens. GFRP composites exhibited larger creep strains in hoop direction, which were exacerbated due to swelling in long-term seawater exposure. The GFRP confining tube, with a lower diameter-to-thickness ratio and higher confining pressure, exhibited improved confinement, increased strength and stiffness, and comparable rupture strain after the combined conditioning process.

KEYWORDS

Seawater and sea-sand concrete (SWSSC); ultra-high-performance concrete (UHPC); GFRP; axial compression; sustained loading; creep; confinement.

INTRODUCTION

The increasing need for concrete manufacturing is responsible for significant carbon dioxide emissions and depletion of finite natural resources, such as freshwater and river sand (Xiao et al., 2017). Seawater and sea sand concrete (SWSSC), manufactured from abundant marine resources can be a sustainable alternative to conventional ordinary Portland cement (OPC) concrete and a prominent solution to this impairment of environmental ecosystem (Ebead et al., 2022; Kaushik & Islam, 1995). Utilizing sea-sand, seawater, and industrial by-products in ultra-high-performance concrete (UHP-SWSSC) manufacture has immense prospects to achieve a viable construction material with improved mechanical (Saleh et al., 2022; Teng et al., 2019), transport, and durability (Saleh et al., 2023) performance. While UHPC offers numerous advantages, the inherent brittleness of UHPC (particularly when unreinforced) poses significant challenges to its widespread application (Hoang & Fehling, 2017).

In the past few decades, fiber reinforced polymers (FRPs) have become widespread in marine constructions (Neşer, 2017), primarily due to their corrosion resistance, high strength-to-weight ratio, and ease of handling and fabrication compared to traditional steel (Ceroni et al., 2006). In concrete filled tubular (CFT) members, FRP wraps and tubes with significant strength along the hoop direction are utilized to confine concrete (Teng & Lam, 2004). In contrast to traditional carbon steel, FRP can be highly compatible with SWSSC for designing advanced hybrid structures that are suitable for use in severe marine environments. Numerous investigations on SWSSC filled FRP tubes have suggested that the use of marine resource based concrete does not notably impact the short-term structural response of such composite structures (Li et al., 2016). Nonetheless, prolonged exposure to seawater and alkaline conditions originating from marine and concrete environments, respectively, may result in the degradation of FRP due to fiber impairment, resin matrix weakening, and fiber-resin interface deterioration (Dong et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2017). One of the efficient approaches to overcome the brittle failure characteristics of UHPC is using it to infill FRP tubes, which results in a hybrid structural member with extremely high bearing capacity and ductility (Zohrevand & Mirmiran, 2011). However,

some studies indicate that the effectiveness of FRP confinement for the inner UHPC core may not be as significant as that of FRP composites filled with normal strength concrete (Guler, 2014). To the best of the authors' knowledge, there is no published literature on the structural performance of FRP encased seawater and sea-sand based UHPC.

It is well-known that some polymeric composite materials exhibit viscoelastic behavior and, as a result, demonstrate time-dependent properties such as creep (Scott et al., 1995). Sustained loading in the presence of moisture can further negatively affect the long-term properties of FRP (Mohan & Adams, 1985), leading to deterioration in their performance. Furthermore, the creep behavior of UHPC varies from those of normal strength concrete due to the significantly high proportion of cementitious binders, extremely low water content, and absence of coarse aggregates (Xu et al., 2018). Presence of a high amount of cementitious materials can increase the basic creep of UHPC (Huang et al., 2023), whereas the low water-to-binder ratio can decrease the drying creep component (Brooks, 2001). Nevertheless, a combination of long-term loading and prolonged marine exposure which represents the service condition of FRP-UHPC composite members can exacerbate their degradation mechanism.

In consideration of the review above, this experimental work investigates the durability performance of UHP-SWSSC filled hybrid FRP tubular columns under combined sustained loading and marine exposure. Glass fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP) with varying diameter to thickness ratio (i.e., 35.7 and 69.3) were utilized as confining tubes. The material properties of the FRPs along the longitudinal and hoop directions were determined by standard axial compression and disc split tensile tests. The composite tubular columns were subjected to long-term loading for 2000 hours under natural seawater exposure at an elevated temperature of 40⁰ C to accelerate their degradation. Creep strains in both longitudinal and transverse directions were monitored throughout the long-term sustained loading – marine exposure period. Full range compressive stress versus longitudinal strains, modulus of elasticity, and failure modes were compared between unconditioned and conditioned FRP encased UHP-SWSSC composite tubes.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

Materials

Based on the manufacturer's data, the mandrel wrapped GFRP tubes were made of S-glass fibers and a Newport 301 (NCT301) semi-toughened, controlled flow epoxy resin system. The laminates for S-Glass had a fiber weight of 300 g/m² with individual ply thickness of 0.27 mm. The thin and thick-walled variant of FRP tubes had a thickness of around 1.5 mm and 3.0 mm, and were denoted as GFRP1.5 and GFRP3.0, respectively. The fibers were oriented along the angles of 0⁰, ±45⁰ and ±60⁰ with respect to the longitudinal axis, which enabled strength and stiffness in both longitudinal and hoop directions. All the tubes had an internal diameter of 101.4 mm and height of 300 mm. Hence, the thin and thick variants of GFRP tubes had an outer diameter to thickness ratio of 35.7 and 69.3, respectively.

A seawater and sea sand based UHPC mix was used as infill to manufacture the hybrid GFRP-UHPC composite tubes. The mixing proportions, mechanical and transport characteristics of this state-of-the-art UHPC can be found in the previously published studies of the authors (Saleh et al., 2022; Saleh et al., 2023). UHP-SWSSC with 50% OPC replaced by 37.5% slag and 12.5% silica fume was found to be the most durable mix and hence utilized as infilled concrete. The GFRP tubes were filled with UHPC immediately after casting, sealed with plastic wraps to avoid moisture loss and were stored in a temperature and moisture controlled cabinet at a temperature of 23⁰ C and a relative humidity of 50%. Three 100 mm diameter × 200 mm height standard concrete cylinders were also fabricated to determine the unconfined compressive strength. The average 28-day compressive strength (f_c') was found to be 122 MPa.

Test methods

Axial compressive tests were performed on hollow GFRP tubes to evaluate their compressive behavior in the longitudinal direction. Unconditioned tubes were cut into 50 mm height and tested on a 1 MN Instron testing machine with 0.5 mm/min loading rate under displacement control. Similar to the

recommendations of Bazli et al., 2020, rubber pads were used on top and bottom of the specimens to avoid local failure at the tube ends. Longitudinal strain and modulus of elasticity were determined from the average of two strain gauges in axial direction attached at the mid-height of the specimens. Material properties of the GFRPs along hoop direction were obtained from ‘split disc’ test according to ASTM D2290-2019. Testing of 20 mm wide GFRP disks were conducted on an Instron 250 kN testing machine with test controls similar to that of axial compressive tests. Two strain gauges in each specimen were attached along the hoop direction to obtain circumferential strain and elastic modulus. The gauges were placed away from the gap at the middle of the half-discs to avoid the local bending effect. Extreme pressure grease was used in the friction surface between the half-discs and GFRP specimen to minimize the influence of friction while loading. Detailed test set-up of such split-disc tests can be found in Li et al. (2016). Unless otherwise specified, the material properties were obtained from the average of three identical specimens for each type of tubes.

UHP-SWSSC filled GFRP tubes were tested in axial compression after 28 days of sealed curing (labeled as “U”, indicating unconditioned tubes). The ends of the composite tubes were ground flat using a high speed diamond saw cutter to ensure simultaneous application of compressive load to both the tube and the concrete. An Instron 2 MN testing machine (test controls similar to the material property tests) was used to conduct the compression tests. Two LVDTs were placed around the samples at an angle of 180 degrees to determine the axial end shortening. The average axial end shortening was divided by the length of composite tubes to calculate the axial strain.

A sustained loading device (as shown in **Figure 1**) was designed to enable the tubular columns to undergo a combination of long-term loading and seawater exposure. An elevated temperature of 40 °C was adopted to accelerate GFRP degradation (Guo et al., 2018) within the relatively short testing timeframe. This exposure condition reflects the service condition of the composite tubes (when used as bridge piers) exposed in harsh marine environments. A transparent acrylic tube was installed inside of a traditional creep rig in order to facilitate the combined conditioning of the specimens. The acrylic tube worked as a seawater bath and therefore rested on a stainless steel base plate to prohibit chloride induced corrosion. Natural seawater (collected from Malabar beach, NSW) at a fixed temperature of 40 °C is continuously circulated between an external temperature controlled stainless-steel water tank and the bath through adequate pumping system. Long-term loading was applied to the GFRP-UHP-SWSSC composite tubes at a sustained load ratio of 0.33 (33% of the short-term compressive load capacity) for 2000 hours. Waterproof strain gauges were installed at the mid-height of tubular columns in both longitudinal and hoop directions to measure the creep strains. After long-term conditioning, the composite tubes were unloaded, and axial compressive tests were carried out to compare the full-range axial stress-strain behavior with the unconditioned specimens. These specimens were labeled with the letter “C”, representing conditioned specimens.

Figure 1: Test set-up for conditioning of composite tubes under sustained load and seawater exposure

TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Material properties of GFRP

Typical stress-strain relationships of GFRPs along the longitudinal and hoop directions are shown in **Figure 2(a)** and **Figure 2(b)**, which were obtained from axial compression and split disc tests, respectively. Young's modulus along longitudinal and hoop directions (E_C and E_T , respectively) were derived from the linear portion of the respective stress-strain diagrams and demonstrated in **Table 1**. Stress-strain curves of the GFRP with lower diameter to thickness ratio (GFRP3.0) exhibited linear behavior until failure in both directions. On the contrary, the GFRP which had higher diameter to thickness ratio (GFRP1.5) showed non-linearity after 0.005 mm/mm strain due to some geometrically nonlinear effects. Ultimate compressive strength (f_{ul}) of the thicker GFRP was found to be approximately 18% higher than the thinner GFRP (220.1 MPa and 260.4 MPa, respectively). Furthermore, the ultimate strains in longitudinal direction (ϵ_{ul}) of GFRP3.0 tube exceeded that of GFRP1.5 (0.0096 and 0.014, respectively).

Table 1. Elastic modulus of GFRP in compression and tension.

Specimen ID	E_C (GPa)	SD (GPa)	E_T (GPa)	SD (GPa)
GFRP1.5	22.8	0.93	21.6	0.79
GFRP3.0	22	1.06	22.9	0.98

Sample size, $n = 3$, SD: standard deviation

From **Figure 2(b)**, ultimate hoop tensile strength (f_{uh}) of 1.5 mm and 3.0 mm thick GFRP rings were 294.0 MPa and 313.0 MPa, respectively. Maximum stresses achieved before failure in hoop direction were higher than those in axial direction for both types of tubes. This is because the failure mode under axial compression was dominated by local buckling. For example, f_{uh} to f_{ul} ratio in GFRP1.5 and GFRP3.0 were found to be 1.2 and 1.34, respectively. No appreciable difference between ϵ_{ul} and ϵ_{uh} were observed for the 3.0 mm GFRPs (0.014 and 0.0156, respectively), whereas the 1.5 mm GFRP had notably larger ultimate strain in the hoop direction (0.0096 and 0.021, respectively). The ultimate strength in both directions was higher in thicker walled tube, possibly because of the higher number of GFRP laminates compared to the thinner counterpart (11 and 6 in GFRP3.0 and GFRP1.5, respectively).

Figure 2: Typical stress-strain curves of GFRP

As demonstrated in **Table 1**, modulus of elasticity of GFRP in axial and transverse directions were comparable. Young's modulus was found to remain unaffected by the diameter to thickness ratio. The properties of the resin matrix and the fiber-resin interface play a significant role in determining the ultimate strength and strain of composite materials (Bazli et al., 2020). However, the elastic modulus is primarily dependent on the modulus of the fibers themselves (Bazli et al., 2020). Typical failure modes observed in the materials property tests are summarized in **Figure 3**. Local buckling along the tube wall

and delamination in the fiber layers are the two modes of failure generally detected in the compressive specimens. The thin walled specimens usually failed with local buckling along the tube perimeter (**Figure 3(a)**), whereas a combined failure mode of local buckling and fiber layer delamination was observed in thick walled specimens (**Figure 3(b)**). The lower interlaminar shear strength of the glass fibers (Wang et al., 2015) may have resulted in early delamination in the layers of fiber plies before wall fracture. Achieving a combined failure mode in GFRPs with thicker walls may explain why they can produce greater ultimate stress and strain compared to their thin-walled counterparts. All the specimens under hoop tensile loading failed due to rupture of fibers (**Figure 3(c)**).

Axial compressive behavior of UHP-SWSSC filled GFRP tubes

A bilinear response was observed from the full-range stress-strain curves of the composite tubes, as shown in **Figure 4**. Similar to the findings reported in (Zohrevand & Mirmiran, 2011), the GFRP3.0 encased UHPC tubes exhibited three distinct regions: a linear elastic region where the FRP tubes were not engaged, a transition region indicating the activation of the confining tubes, and a strain hardening region where the FRP tubes were fully engaged, and the dilation of the core UHPC was resisted. A sudden stress relaxation was noticed immediately after the first peak due to the local buckling of GFRP tube along the longitudinal direction (Li et al., 2016). However, depending on the confinement efficiency of the outer FRP tubes, a subsequent ascending (or sometimes descending) stress-strain response can be achieved (Wang et al., 2018). The first buckling stress of the composite specimens were similar (in the range of 122-127 MPa) regardless of the diameter-to-thickness ratio of the FRP. However, the later enhancement of rupture strain varied significantly. The GFRP1.5-U specimen failed immediately after the first buckling and engagement of the confining tube. It is well established that the efficacy of FRP confinement depends on the confining pressure provided by the outer tubes (Zohrevand & Mirmiran, 2011), which is a function of their hoop tensile elastic moduli, hoop rupture strain, thickness and the diameter of the concrete core (Guler, 2014)). In the current study, the GFRP1.5-U specimen failed shortly after reaching the first buckling stress because the confining stiffness produced

Figure 4: Axial stress-strain curves of unconditioned UHPC filled composite GFRP tubes

by the thinner and weaker GFRP with relatively lower hoop strength was insufficient to provide effective confinement to the high-strength UHPC core (Teng et al., 2009). Interestingly, ultimate rupture strain (ϵ_{th}) for the thinner GFRP tube was significantly low compared to ultimate material hoop strain (ϵ_{uh}) obtained from split disc test (0.0038 and 0.021, respectively). Insufficient confining pressure offered by GFRP with lesser thickness prevented the outer tube from reaching its material capacity, and thereby leading to a premature failure of hybrid tubular column. Conversely, ϵ_{th} of GFRP3.0-U agreed well with ϵ_{uh} (0.017 and 0.0156, respectively), indicating their superior confinement effect.

The effectiveness of FRP confinement in enhancing strength and ductility of composite columns is known to decrease with the increase in unconfined strength of the concrete core (Cui & Sheikh, 2010). GFRP composite tubes displayed a noticeably smaller improvement in ultimate compressive strength compared to the unconfined UHPC cylinders. The maximum compressive stress of GFRP1.5 and GFRP3.0 specimens were 130.9 MPa and 133.9 MPa, offering a 6.8% and 9.8% strength enhancement compared to the unwrapped UHPC, respectively. Level of external confinement needs to be significant to facilitate strength enhancement of ultra-high strength core concrete (Dang et al., 2022), which was not achieved by the GFRP tubes with relatively lesser hoop tensile strength, especially compared to CFRPs (Li et al., 2016). A comprehensive study is currently underway to determine a more accurate degree of strength enhancement of the UHPC core confined by different FRP tubes.

Conditioning of composite tubes under sustained load and marine exposure

Creep properties

A comparison of long-term strains of GFRP composite specimens along both longitudinal and transverse directions is demonstrated in **Figure 5**. The longitudinal long-term strains are governed by the creep and shrinkage of the UHP-SWSSC infills, which can be substantial due to its very high cementitious content (Huang et al., 2023). Nonetheless, the comparison among different FRP-UHPC composites can indicate the influence and confinement efficiency of the outer FRP tubes in their long-

term performance. It is evident from **Figure 5(a)** that the longitudinal creep increases with the increase in diameter to thickness ratio of the outer GFRP. The creep strains were measured at 722×10^{-6} and 587×10^{-6} mm/mm after 2000 hours in GFRP1.5 and GFRP3.0, respectively. This aligns with the findings of Bouziadi et al., (2020) indicating that the increase in fiber layer thickness can enhance the overall robustness of the composite structure and effectively reduce creep. However, as shown in **Figure 5(b)**, creep in hoop direction was independent of the thickness of confining FRP layer.

Another interesting phenomenon to note is that while the longitudinal creep stabilized after around 700 hours, the transverse creep strains increased significantly, especially after 1000 hours. This may have occurred due to the swelling of GFRP composites exposed to liquid medium, which enables the

rearrangement of the macromolecules and thereby an increase in the creep rate (Panasyuk et al., 1988). Additionally, long-term exposure to an elevated temperature can further accelerate the creep associated with moisture exposure. Unlike carbon fiber, glass fibers deteriorate when exposed to seawater and alkaline concrete environments (Bazli et al., 2020; Rossini et al., 2019). Intrusion of moisture and diffusion of alkaline chemicals can cause leaching and etching of the glass fibers and lead to degradation in the fiber structure. The glass fiber matrix can also deteriorate through plasticization, interface debonding, swelling, osmotic cracking, etc. (Li et al., 2018). The overall softening of GFRP fiber, matrix and their interface can degrade the stiffness of FRP composite and thus lead to progressively higher creep strains, especially in the later exposure period (Bouziadi et al., 2020). Beyond 1000 hours of exposure, the transverse creep strains were substantially large in GFRP composites compared to creep in axial direction. For instance, the longitudinal and transverse creep coefficients (ratio of the creep strain to the instantaneous strain) in GFRP3.0 were 0.45 and 3.12 after 2000 hours marine exposure, respectively. In general, the GFRP encased UHP-SWSSC hybrid tubes demonstrate improved resistance to longitudinal creep compared to those in hoop direction. This research group is currently conducting a comprehensive investigation to evaluate the effects of long-term loading and environmental exposure individually.

Comparison of axial compressive behavior

Figure 6 compares the full-range stress-strain response of unconditioned and conditioned composite specimens under axial compression. It is evident that long-term sustained loading and marine exposure did not alter the shape of the stress-strain curves. In addition, the combined creep-exposure conditioning did not have any negative effects on the strength as well as ductility of the tubular columns. The conditioned specimens even exhibited slightly higher compressive strength compared to their unconditioned counterparts, and the reason behind this phenomenon can be threefold. Firstly, the continuous pressure applied during the creep tests can accelerate the hydration reactions in cementitious composites (Coutinho, 1977), resulting in enhanced strength. Secondly, the slower propagation of microcracks, attributed to a relatively lower level of sustained loading (30% - 70% of the maximum short-term capacity as reported in Claisse & Dean, 2013) allows for autogenous healing as the Portlandite in the hydrated cement matrix produces insoluble calcite (CaCO_3) (Neville, 1996). And finally, long-term sustained loading effectively increases the van der Waals forces (Hellesland & Green, 1972), bringing the hydration gel particles closer together and densifying the matrix. From **Table 2**, the modulus of elasticity in thin-walled conditioned GFRP tube was found to be slightly lower than the unconditioned specimens, whereas the thick-walled tube displayed a slight enhancement in stiffness. Creep in composite cross-section can result in stress redistributions and transfer more stress from the concrete core to the confining tubes. This, in turn, enhances the stiffness by increasing the degree of composite interactions between the two components (Younas et al., 2021). However, the relatively low confining pressure exerted by the GFRP tubes with greater diameter to thickness ratio appears to be inadequate in sustaining the distributed stress. As a result, an improvement in the composite actions is hindered, which ultimately leads to a reduction in Young’s modulus. As demonstrated in **Table 2**, enhancement of ultimate compressive strength after conditioning was also much smaller in GFRP1.5 compared to GFRP3.0 (6.2% and 13.6%, respectively).

Table 2. Elastic modulus and maximum stress of GFRP-UHPC composite tubes before and after exposure

Specimen ID (outer tube type)	E_U (GPa)	Maximum stress (MPa)	E_C (GPa)	Maximum stress (MPa)
GFRP1.5	48.6	130.3	44.8	138.3
GFRP3.0	45.5	133.9	47.8	151.9
Note: E_U : Elastic modulus of unconditioned specimens, E_C : Elastic modulus of conditioned specimens.				

Figure 6: Comparison of axial stress-strain curves between unconditioned and conditioned composite tubes

Failure modes of the composite tubes

Figure 7 demonstrates the failure modes of the unconditioned and conditioned composite tubes. Failure in GFRP1.5 composite specimen before and after conditioning occurred without any apparent damage to the GFRP. Hence, the GFRP tubes were carefully cut and split open to facilitate the inspection of the internal UHPC cores. Upon examination, significant cracking was detected within the inner cores. In this case, failure in the confinement did not take place, as concrete was not effectively confined by thinner GFRP with low confining pressure (Li et al., 2018). On the other hand, failure mode for the 3.0 mm GFRP confined UHP-SWSSC tube was FRP tube rupture in the hoop direction and crushing of concrete core. Additionally, it is perceived from **Figure 4** that the GFRP3.0 composite specimen experiencing hoop rupture failure of the outer tube was also able to achieve significant ultimate axial strains, which aligns with the findings reported by Li et al., 2016.

Figure 7: Comparison of failure modes between unconditioned and conditioned specimens

In general, the conditioning of the composite tubes did not alter their failure behavior, except that the hoop rupture of the confining GFRP3.0 tube was more explosive. This may be attributed to the densification of UHPC matrix under sustained loading. Similar to the unconditioned specimen, the conditioned GFRP1.5 exhibited premature failure with minimal core cracking. It appears that the confinement pressure provided by the thin GFRP further deteriorated under environmental exposure, resulting in its inability to effectively restrain the dilation of the UHPC core through the "passive confinement effect" (Li et al., 2016).

CONCLUSION

Based on the limited experimental data presented in this paper, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- From the material properties investigated, the ultimate compressive and hoop tensile strength of GFRP increased as the diameter to thickness ratio decreased, whereas the elastic modulus remained unaffected. The average ratio of hoop tensile to longitudinal compressive strength was in the range of 1.2-1.34.
- During the axial compression of GFRP encased UHP-SWSSC tubes, initial local buckling occurred at a comparable stress level. However, the subsequent strain hardening and the ultimate rupture strain were influenced by the confinement effectiveness of outer GFRP confinement. Thicker GFRP tube in composite columns could achieve its material hoop rupture strains, whereas the thin-walled GFRP composites failed before reaching its material capacity. Lower confinement pressure provided by the GFRP tubes inhibited the strength enhancement of the confined UHPC core.
- Creep strains along longitudinal direction stabilized after 700 hours, whereas transverse creep increased noticeably, especially after 1000 hours of combined sustained load and seawater exposure. Transverse creep of composite tubes was exacerbated by swelling of GFRP in marine environments and was higher than longitudinal creep after long-term exposure.
- Long-term sustained loading and marine exposure had no detrimental effects on the strength, ductility, and failure modes of the composite tubes. The GFRP tube with lower diameter to thickness ratio and subsequent higher confining pressure could effectively confine the UHPC core and resulted in enhanced strength, stiffness, and comparable ultimate strain following the combined conditioning process.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.